

SND Strategic Plan 2018–2022

Vision and Aims

Introduction

The purpose of Swedish National Data Service (SND) is to provide a coordinated and secure structure for describing, depositing, sharing, and finding research data. SND is governed by a consortium consisting of seven universities: University of Gothenburg, Karolinska Institutet, Lund University, Stockholm University, Swedish University of Agricultural Sciences, Umeå University, and Uppsala University. From 2018 to 2022 SND will undergo major changes to develop, grow, and expand its activities. The organization will support nearly 30 universities in establishing and running local data access units (DAUs). By the end of the period, the efforts will have had a crucial impact on researchers' abilities to reuse FAIR data, nationally and internationally.

The focus of *SND Strategic Plan 2018-2022* is to declare our vision and describe the strategic objectives of the national research infrastructure. The strategic plan consists of two parts:

1. The vision with a short description of the mission and the overall purpose of the infrastructure
2. The three overarching strategic areas with specified aims:
 - a. Facilitate and Secure Research Data and Metadata Flows
 - b. Assist and Benefit Users
 - c. Accumulate and Maintain Expertise

In addition to the strategic plan, SND will present annual operational plans, including important priorities for the coming year, time schedules and specified action points for each aim.

Our vision

Our vision is to be part of a global network through which researchers can easily share, find, access and reuse high-quality research data – now and in the future. We will make this happen by inspiring, energizing, and coordinating the development of a trustworthy system of research data repositories in Sweden.

Facilitate and Secure Research Data and Metadata Flows

Aims:

- To develop a network of Trusted Digital Repositories.
Comment: SND will facilitate the establishment of a national system of Trusted Digital Repositories, distributed across Swedish universities. This system will have a joint metadata registry and research data discovery service.

- To provide systems, interfaces and services for finding, accessing and reusing FAIR-compliant data and metadata.
Comment: SND will develop systems that allow management and sharing of high-quality data documentation and ensure that all research data found in the SND metadata registry have persistent identifiers. The interfaces will build on SND's existing metadata registry and dissemination service but will be further developed to support automated harvesting and discipline-appropriate input of metadata.

- To extend high-level curation routines to cover a broader range of data.
Comment: New routines will be implemented and the routines that SND already has in place for certain types of data will be developed to cover a broader range of data types and be suitable to more research disciplines.

- To promote research data of significant potential.
Comment: SND will actively promote research data which are considered to have significant potential – scientific, historical and/or international – for secondary research. These data will be identified through an Acquisition Policy.

Assist and Benefit Users

Aims:

- To train and support DAUs and researchers in research data management and curation.
Comment: This includes for instance providing up-to-date teaching and training material, arranging workshops and conferences, providing up-to-date best practices and guidelines. SND will help institutions in establishing local DAUs.

- To be the hub in a network of DAUs at Swedish institutions.
Comment: SND will coordinate the DAU network, and a central role will be to promote knowledge exchange between DAUs, and between DAUs and SND. SND will also actively work to extend the collaboration with additional institutions.

- To facilitate for network institutions to get certified as Trusted Digital Repositories.
Comment: In order to increase quality SND will strive to encourage and support network institutions in their attempts to become certified, and in parallel negotiate ways in which DAU/SND systems can have one joint certification.

- To actively promote Open Science and in particular the sharing and reuse of research data, nationally and internationally.
Comment: SND will work to make research data sharing recognised as a valid research output as well as a valuable contribution to the scientific community, and to promote the use of data citation and the FAIR principles. SND will also encourage and support advancement of methods for secondary analysis of research data. This work will largely be done in collaboration with the DAUs.

Accumulate and Maintain Expertise

Aims:

- To be a well-functioning consortium with integrated domain expert functions.
Comment: To integrate all parts of the consortium to a well-functioning unified research infrastructure supporting researchers from an increasing number of scientific domains. This will include managing extensive knowledge exchange between all members of the consortium.

- To maintain an up-to-date, wide range of competencies and comprehensive knowledge within management, curation, and documentation of research data.
Comment: This will include for instance compiling up-to-date best practices and guidelines, developing and adjusting data curation methods, workflows and standards.

- To strengthen and widen domain-specific data expertise.
Comment: The strengthening and widening of data expertise will be carried out in close collaboration with researchers and will be dependent on the needs and requirements of the designated community.

- To monitor and to be an integrated part of the national and international research data ecosystem.
Comment: The research data ecosystem is in constant development. The national and international changes in this area requires a constant monitoring of trends, policies, decisions etc. in order to give researchers and other important stakeholders the best services possible.